

Foundation model for Fast Simulation

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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This project focuses on leveraging large-scale transformer-based models, inspired by recent advancements in AI such as GPT-3 and DALL-E-2, for fast simulation in high-energy physics (HEP) experiments. Fast simulation plays a critical role in testing hypotheses and generating simulated samples, but the demand for speed and scale necessitates innovative approaches. The student will delve into understanding fast simulation, previous works in this field, and the design of our transformer-based model. Their contribution will involve enhancing data preprocessing and designing specialized loss functions, ultimately aiming to accelerate HEP experiments and advance our understanding of fundamental physics through cutting-edge AI-driven simulations.

ABSTRACT

In the pursuit of enhancing fast simulation for the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments, this report focuses on the development of foundation models with a crucial emphasis on achieving highly accurate predictions and simulations. The research entails the comparison of generated shower simulations with their input counterparts, employing various evaluation metrics to gauge the performance. The chosen architecture for this endeavor is the VQVAE model, which underpins the critical role of preprocessing and loss functions in achieving success. Through a series of meticulous experiments, the study seeks to identify the most effective combinations of preprocessing techniques and loss functions, ultimately revealing that the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" preprocessing technique, coupled with the Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss function, surpasses all other explored methodologies for reconstruction task. This finding underscores the significance of tailored preprocessing and objective functions in achieving the project's objectives, promising more accurate and reliable simulations for the LHC experiments

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	06
<hr/>	
DATASET DESCRIPTION	07
<hr/>	
ARCHITECTURE	09
<hr/>	
EXISTING CHALLENGES	10
<hr/>	
PREPROCESSING TECHNIQUES	10
Scaling wrt Incident Energy	
Zero-centering and scaling wrt incident energy	
Standardizing	
Total Energy per layer Scaling	
Maximum Energy per layer Scaling	
<hr/>	
LOSS FUCNTIONS	14
Mean Square Error(MSE)	
L1 Loss	
BCE	
Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD)	
Weighted BCE	
Weighted MSE	

Weighted BCE + L1 loss (Mean Absolute Error)

Weighted MSE

EVALUATION METRICS	18
RESULTS	19
FUTURE WORK	19
CONCLUSION	29
RÉFÉRENCES	29

1. INTRODUCTION

In Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments, particle detectors, particularly calorimeters, are essential for measuring particle energy. Particles from collisions interact with the calorimeter material, generating cascades of secondary particles known as showers. Precise simulation of these showers is critical but computationally intensive. The upcoming High Luminosity upgrade of the LHC will amplify the demand for simulation due to increased event complexity, placing greater strain on computing resources.

Simulation in experimental particle physics involves predicting detector-level physics processes, aiding detector design and physics analyses. Accurate detector response simulation is essential for understanding and matching theoretical predictions to experimental measurements. These simulations use Monte Carlo methods, combining randomness and computational algorithms, to approximate complex particle showers and estimate probability distributions. By iteratively simulating physics at various scales, these techniques facilitate comprehensive physics exploration and validation.

Fast simulation techniques are crucial in particle physics due to the time-consuming nature of simulating particle interactions with detector materials. Rather than meticulously simulating the entire cascade of particles in detectors, fast simulation methods opt for parametrizing energy deposition and generating all hits in a single step. This expedites the simulation process significantly, allowing researchers to efficiently analyze data, design detectors, and perform physics experiments, especially in the context of high-luminosity experiments where computational demands are substantial. Fast simulation strikes a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency, making it an essential tool in modern particle physics research. Fast Simulation is broadly divided into two types: classical and machine learning approaches. Classical fast simulation methods, exemplified by techniques like Gflash, involve parameterizing the characteristics of electromagnetic and hadronic showers in particle detectors. These methods employ mathematical formulas to describe the longitudinal and lateral shower profiles, enabling quicker simulations of particle interactions within the detector material.

In contrast, machine learning approaches for fast simulation leverage generative models within the field of High-Energy Physics (HEP) applications. These generative models are designed to accelerate the process of simulating detector responses. Further details on these models can be found in the following section, highlighting how one of the machine learning techniques is harnessed to enhance the speed and efficiency of particle detector simulations in HEP research.

Preprocessing and loss functions play pivotal roles in the workflow of this simulation project. The preprocessing step not only readies the simulated data by cleaning and scaling it but also encodes essential conditional information, allowing for the creation of universal shower representations. These representations are then utilized in training the generative model. As the model's hyperparameters are optimized and it undergoes validation, it ultimately gets converted into a format suitable for inference. The optimization techniques employed during inference, like quantization and graph optimizations, further enhance the model's efficiency by reducing memory requirements. In essence, the success of the entire workflow hinges on the effectiveness of preprocessing and the choice of appropriate loss functions, which are fundamental for accurate and efficient simulation outcomes. Therefore, we primarily focus on exploring preprocessing techniques and refining loss functions to enhance both the performance and convergence of the simulation workflow. These critical components are pivotal in achieving accurate and efficient outcomes in this project, where data preparation and model optimization are central to success.

2. DATASET DESCRIPTION

In our research, we leverage a subset of an existing dataset generated using Geant4 simulations for calorimeter studies. The dataset covers a range of particle showers involving electrons or photons with energies spanning from 1 GeV to 1 TeV and incident angles from 50° to 90° in 10° increments. The particles approach the detector perpendicular to the z-axis at a 90° entrance angle.

Fig.1 Cylindrical Energy mesh in the direction of momentum of particle

The dataset provides a diverse set of particle interactions, considering variations in energy, incident angles, and detector materials. It encompasses simplified setups, such as concentric cylinders with alternating layers of materials (SiW and SciPb), as well as more realistic geometries inspired by the CLIC detector layout for the Future Circular Collider's electron-positron collider experiment (FCC-ee).

To capture the intricacies of particle showers, we employ a scoring mesh within the detector, maintaining a granularity of $18 \times 50 \times 45$, representing 18 steps along the radius, 50 angular segments, and 45 layers. This allows us to handle the complexity arising from a wide range of input domains and ensures consistent segmentation independent of detector readout specifications.

The dataset preprocessing involves converting Geant4-generated ROOT files into the machine learning-friendly HDF5 format. This step not only facilitates model training but also incorporates additional information such as detector identifiers (SiW, SciPb) using one-hot encoding, and the

energy and angle of the incoming particles. The dataset, with its diverse scenarios and nuanced granularity, provides a robust foundation for machine learning analysis, addressing the complexities inherent in calorimeter studies.

Fig.2 Cylindrical mesh granularity for the chosen experiments

The dataset's higher granularity, set at 18x50x45, introduces increased complexity by providing finer details of particle interactions within the calorimeter. This heightened granularity, coupled with the inherent sparsity of the data—around 90%—poses challenges for analysis. Additionally, the long input range contributes further to the intricacy of the dataset, requiring careful consideration in machine learning model design and interpretation.

3. ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we detail the core architecture and methodology employed in our experiment, which focuses on regenerating the mesh response based on incident energy, incident angle, and calorimeter geometry. Our approach leverages the powerful Vector Quantized Variational Autoencoder (VQ-VAE) architecture, tailored to the specific requirements of our task.

At the heart of our approach lies the VQ-VAE architecture, which plays a central role in encoding, decoding, and generating mesh responses. The architecture comprises three key components: encoder, vector quantization and decoder. The encoder processes the input data, compressing it into a discrete latent space. This latent space captures essential features of the input, enabling

effective data compression and representation. We are using a transformer based encoder rather than a simple neural network due to the fact that transformers have potential to scale and capture better encodings due to attention mechanisms.

Fig.3 Architecture - Vector Quantized Variational AutoEncoders (VQ-VAE)

A critical step in our methodology, vector quantization maps the continuous latent space into discrete codes or symbols. These codes represent the structured information contained within the latent space. The decoder, working in tandem with the quantized codes, reverses the encoding process to reconstruct the original data format. In our case, it regenerates the mesh response. Like encoder, it is also composed of transformer blocks.

After the model has learned the encoding and decoding relationships, we transition into the auto-regressive phase. Here, the latent space representation becomes conditioned on specific context, including incident energy, incident angle, and calorimeter geometry. This conditioning empowers our model to generate mesh responses directly from these provided conditionals, without the need to explicitly utilize the entire encoded latent space. This context-aware capability is pivotal for achieving accurate and meaningful reconstructions of the calorimeter response within our experimental setup.

It is worth noting that our experiments primarily focus on autoencoder architecture. There are several challenges associated with optimizing VQ-VAE, particularly in the context of our experiment, due to the discrete nature of latent space in case of autoencoders and codebook initialization..

4. EXISTING CHALLENGES

In a technical context, our dataset presents two notable challenges. Firstly, it grapples with high sparsity, largely stemming from the intricacies of our fine-grained measurements. Approximately 90% of the entries in our data are populated with zeros, indicating a scarcity of non-zero values. This sparsity introduces significant hurdles for machine learning algorithms, which often rely on data patterns to make accurate predictions or reconstructions. In the presence of such sparse data, these algorithms encounter difficulties in discerning meaningful information, potentially leading to suboptimal performance or inaccurate modeling.

Secondly, our dataset includes high-energy voxels, which hold immense significance within the context of our simulation task. These high-energy cells contain crucial information that is indispensable for accurately representing the underlying physical processes in our study. Ignoring or downplaying these high-energy data points is not a viable solution, as they constitute pivotal components of our dataset. Thus, addressing the sparsity issue while retaining the integrity and relevance of these high-energy voxels poses a formidable challenge that requires specialized approaches and methodologies to tackle effectively in our analysis.

Fig.4 Figure showing sparsity of cell energies

5. PREPROCESSING DATA

Preprocessing is vital for our problem as it converts diverse input data, majorly the energy mesh, including incident energy, angle, and geometry, into a structured format suitable for machine learning. Moreover, it aligns the data with the requirements of the VQ-VAE architecture, enhancing the model's capacity to generate accurate mesh responses. Preprocessing techniques studied during the project are discussed below:

a. Scaling wrt Incident Energy

The primary motivation behind this preprocessing method is to normalize the energy values in the dataset, scaling them between 0 and 1. By doing so, we aim to frame the problem as a probability model, allowing us to utilize the sigmoid activation function at the output layer. This approach simplifies the modeling process and makes it conducive for predicting probabilities associated with energy values.

$$x = \frac{x}{E_i}$$

where x represents cell energy and E_i represents incident energy.

While this method offers the advantage of probability modeling, it comes with certain limitations. One of them is that this preprocessing technique may not adequately capture the cell energy distribution, potentially leading to information loss in modeling. Thus, while it simplifies the problem, it might not fully address the nuances of the underlying physics, and it's important to assess its impact on the model's performance in terms of accuracy and distribution representation.

b. Zero-centering and scaling wrt incident energy

In the data preprocessing phase, zero-centering and scaling with respect to the incident energy were implemented as an initial step in addressing potential convergence challenges in achieving high cell energy voxels.

$$x = \frac{(x - \bar{x})}{E_i}$$

where x represents cell energy, $\bar{x}$ represents mean energy and E_i represents incident energy.

The underlying objective of this approach was to assess the impact of zero-centering on the convergence of our machine learning model. However, it became evident that the inherent skewness of the data remained a significant obstacle, despite the rigorous application of zero-centering. Consequently, the data's skewed distribution continued to persist even after scaling, indicating that further exploration of tailored preprocessing techniques is warranted to effectively manage this distinct data characteristic.

c. Standardizing

Standardization involves subtracting the mean from each data point and then scaling it by the total standard deviation of the dataset. Mathematically, this process can be represented as follows:

$$x = \frac{(x - \bar{x})}{SD(x)}$$

where where x represents cell energy, $\bar{x}$ represents mean energy and $SD(x)$ represents standard deviation of cell energy distribution.

Fig.5 Comparison of cell energies distribution with original preprocessing(i.e. to scaling down with incident energy), standardization and zero-centering

The motivation behind incorporating standardization into our preprocessing workflow was to investigate its effect on the distribution of cell energy values. Figure 5 presents a visual representation of the cell energy distribution after applying standardization, and a comparative analysis with the previously discussed zero-centering technique. Notably, the figure illustrates that standardization results in a less steep decline in cell energy distribution compared to zero-centering. This observation is of significant importance as it suggests that standardization effectively mitigates the skewness in the data distribution, providing a more desirable and centered distribution of cell energy values.

d. Total Energy per layer Scaling

This method involved the division of cell energies within each layer by the total energy of that specific layer. Mathematically, this process can be expressed as follows:

$$x_{(i)(l)} = \frac{x_{(i)(l)}}{\sum x_{(l)}}$$

where $x_{(i)(l)}$ represents i th cell energy in the l th layer, and the denominator represents the sum of all energies in the l th layer.

The underlying rationale behind this approach was to simplify the complexity of the problem at hand. By scaling cell energies within a layer to be relative proportions of the total energy in that layer, the objective was to transform the problem into a more tractable task. Specifically, this preprocessing method aimed to facilitate the prediction of cell energy intensity within a layer, conditioned on the total energies of that layer. This was motivated by the idea that modeling the intensity of cell energies as relative proportions within a layer could provide valuable insights and simplify the prediction task.

However, it's important to note that this approach also introduced a challenge. Predicting total energies for each layer separately, while conditioning on factors such as incident energy, angle, and calorimeter geometry, added an additional layer of complexity to the overall modeling problem. This further underscored the need for a comprehensive understanding of the trade-offs and intricacies involved in implementing the "Total Energy per Layer Scaling" technique within our research.

Fig.6 Total Energy per layer scaling in which all cell energies are divided by sum of energies of their layer

e. Maximum Energy per layer Scaling

It involves normalizing cell energies within each layer by dividing them by the maximum energy value present in that particular layer. Mathematically, this can be expressed as:

$$x_{(i)(l)} = \frac{x_{(i)(l)}}{\max(x_{(l)})}$$

where $x_{(i)(l)}$ represents i th cell energy in the l th layer, and the denominator represents the maximum of all energies in the l th layer.

The rationale behind implementing this technique was to simplify the problem complexity by modeling the prediction of cell energy intensities within a layer relative to the maximum energy value in that layer. This approach aimed to make the problem more manageable by relating each cell's energy to the layer's maximum, thereby providing a more interpretable metric.

However, it's crucial to note that predicting maximum energy values, while conditioning on factors such as incident energy, angle, and calorimeter geometry, introduced an added layer of complexity. This is particularly challenging due to the considerable variation and instability in maximum energy values, which significantly impact all cell energies within the layer.

Fig.7 Scaling Cell Energies within Each Layer by Dividing by the Maximum Layer Energy

Thus, the prediction of maximum energy values presents a more intricate problem compared to total energies, and it requires careful consideration and analysis to accurately capture the dynamics underlying these fluctuations.

6. LOSS FUNCTIONS

The importance of the loss function in our project cannot be overstated, as it defines our model's optimization goal, guiding parameter tuning to improve its performance. Experimenting with different loss functions allows us to compare and determine which formulation best aligns with our project's objectives, ensuring that the model's behavior closely matches our desired outcomes.

a. Mean Square Error(MSE)

The Mean Square Error (MSE) loss function was initially employed as a reconstruction loss in our project. MSE is a commonly used metric for quantifying the discrepancy between the model's predictions and the actual target values. It is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ell(x, y) &= L = \{l_1, \dots, l_N\}^T, \\ l_n &= (x_n - y_n)^2 \end{aligned}$$

where x_n represents n th cell energy in a certain event and y_n represents reconstructed n th cell energy.

However, it became apparent that while the MSE loss was decreasing during training, the model was not effectively learning the underlying data characteristics. This paradoxical behavior was observed, where the loss was diminishing, but the model's representations and metrics were essentially converging to the mean of the data distribution.

In the context of our project, this loss was utilized as a means to evaluate the fidelity of the reconstructed data from the model. The decreasing MSE suggested that, on average, the model's predictions were getting closer to the true values. However, this led to the realization that the MSE loss alone might not be suitable for our specific problem. While it measures the overall reconstruction quality, it may not capture the more intricate patterns and relationships within the data.

b. L1 Loss

The L1 Loss, also known as the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) loss, was adopted as an alternative to the Mean Square Error (MSE) loss in our project. The intuition behind employing L1 Loss was to capture sharper deviations and prioritize the modeling of absolute differences between the desired values and the model's predictions, rather than focusing on the means or squared differences.

The L1 Loss is mathematically defined as:

$$l(x,y)=L=\{l_1, \dots, l_N\}^T$$

$$l_n = |x_n - y_n|$$

where x_n represents n th cell energy in a certain event and y_n represents reconstructed n th cell energy.

Here, N represents the total number of data points, x signifies the actual target values, and y represents the model's predicted values. Unlike the MSE, which squares the differences between predictions and actual values, the L1 Loss calculates the absolute differences. This formulation makes L1 Loss robust in capturing sharp deviations and outliers within the data, emphasizing the magnitude of the errors without being influenced by the square term.

By utilizing the L1 Loss, we aimed to provide the model with a more sensitive measure for evaluating and penalizing errors in the prediction process.

c. BCE

The Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss function is calculated using the following formula:

$$loss = BCELoss(y_{hat}, y)$$

or

$$loss = -\frac{1}{N} \sum [(y_i * \log(y_{pred})) + ((1 - y_i) * \log(1 - y_{pred}))]$$

where y_i represents i th cell energy in a certain event and y_{pred} represents reconstructed i th cell energy.

In the project, Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss was applied to values that lie in a continuous range from 0 to 1, which aligns with its conventional use for binary outcomes. Despite this alignment, the challenge arose when trying to accurately model the right tail of the distribution of

cell energies within this continuous range. While BCE loss can effectively handle the overall learning of the model for energies, but it could not force the extreme cell values i.e.(very few 1s than 0s). Nonetheless, BCE loss performed well in achieving other profiles of the data, highlighting the need for a more specialized approach to address the issue of cell energies distribution.

d. Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD)

The Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) loss is used for measuring the dissimilarity between two probability distributions. It is commonly employed in tasks where the objective is to align two distributions or to assess the similarity between observed data and model-generated data. The intuition behind MMD is to minimize the discrepancy between the distributions, thereby improving the model's ability to generate data that closely resembles the observed data distribution.

$$MMD(P, Q) = \| E_{X \sim P}[\varphi(X)] - E_{Y \sim Q}[\varphi(Y)] \|_H$$

where P and Q represent two distributions from which X and Y are sampled. Function $\varphi()$ represents features of distribution and mean of these features is made close.

The MMD loss aims to minimize the difference between the pairwise similarities (expressed through the kernel function) of data points in the two distributions, ultimately encouraging the model to generate data that closely matches the observed distribution, and this is what we desire to learn that our generated distribution approximates the input cell energy distribution.

The implementation of Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) loss within the context of this project is applied to the output space, specifically to the generated events' data distribution and the input data distribution. This approach focuses on minimizing the divergence between these two distributions by reducing the feature differences, with the aim of improving the model's ability to generate data that closely aligns with the characteristics of the input data.

It's important to note that in the broader literature and various machine learning applications, MMD loss can be applied not only in the output space but also in the latent space. In the latent space, MMD loss serves a similar purpose by minimizing the divergence between data distributions, though it is often used in conjunction with other techniques such as the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence. Applying MMD in the latent space typically aims to improve the mapping of data to a lower-dimensional representation or latent space, thereby facilitating more effective data generation or clustering.

e. Weighted BCE

Weighted Binary Cross-Entropy (WBCE) loss was experimented, which is an extension of the Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss. The core idea behind WBCE is to assign different weights to different classes or data points based on their significance. In your case, the intuition was to penalize higher cell energies more than lower ones by assigning higher weights to the loss associated with these higher values.

The motivation behind this approach lies in the scarcity of higher cell energy values and the importance of accurately learning and representing them. By assigning greater weight to the loss associated with higher cell energies, the model is encouraged to focus more on modeling and predicting these critical, albeit less frequent, values. This weighting strategy effectively highlights

the significance of higher cell energies in the overall learning process, ensuring that the model pays special attention to these data points while optimizing its predictions.

The formula for the Weighted Binary Cross-Entropy loss is similar to the standard BCE loss, but it introduces weights for different classes or data points.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{loss} &= \text{BCELoss}(y_{\text{hat}}, y) \\ w &= 1 + c * e^{c*y}, \text{when } y \neq 0 \\ w &= 1 \quad \quad \quad \text{when } y = 0 \\ \text{weightedLoss} &= w * \text{loss} \end{aligned}$$

where c represents a constant known as weight balancing coefficient, y represents input data and y_{hat} represents reconstructed data.

f. Weighted BCE + L1 loss (Mean Absolute Error)

The combination of Weighted Binary Cross-Entropy (WBCE) and L1 loss in our project represents a well-thought-out strategy that strikes a balance between two critical aspects of the problem. The first part of this approach, the WBCE loss, was chosen to effectively capture binary-ranged outcomes, where certain events or decisions are of utmost importance in your project's context. By assigning different weights to data points, the model is guided to focus on classifying these events accurately, ensuring that it learns the critical decision boundaries.

The second component, the L1 loss, adds another layer of sophistication by emphasizing the magnitude and absolute differences in data values. This is particularly valuable when there are sharp deviations or outliers in the data distribution, which carry significant information in your project. The combination of these two loss functions intelligently leverages the strengths of each, providing a holistic approach to address the multifaceted nature of your research, where both classification accuracy and precise representation of data deviations are crucial for achieving the desired outcomes. This hybrid approach aligns with the intuitive understanding that achieving a comprehensive understanding of the data may require attending to different aspects simultaneously.

g. Weighted MSE

The experimentation with Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss represents a comprehensive effort to investigate the efficacy of introducing weightings to loss functions in your project. This approach serves as a broad exploration to determine whether the relative weighting of loss components can enhance the performance of various loss functions. It is defined in the same way as WBCE loss:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{loss} &= \text{MSELoss}(y_{\text{hat}}, y) \\ w &= 1 + c * e^{c*y}, \text{when } y \neq 0 \\ w &= 1 \quad \quad \quad \text{when } y = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$weightedLoss = w * loss$$

where c represents a constant known as weight balancing coefficient, y represents input data and y_{hat} represents reconstructed data.

The core intuition behind using WMSE lies in its flexibility to adapt to diverse aspects of your data. By assigning different weights to different data points or components, you can steer the optimization process in the desired direction. This technique allows you to focus the model's attention on the most critical aspects of your problem, whether it be capturing variations, emphasizing specific data ranges, or highlighting outlier values. The exploration of WMSE reflects a valuable strategy for achieving a balanced and fine-tuned approach to modeling your data.

7. Evaluation Metrics

Total Energy: This metric is essential for assessing the distribution of total energies in both input and generated data, providing insights into how closely the frequency of total energies aligns between the two distributions.

Lateral Profile: The lateral profile measures the sum of energies at different radial points across all layers. It's valuable for understanding the distribution of energy across radial points, which can offer insights into the spatial characteristics of events.

Longitudinal Profile: The longitudinal profile evaluates the sum of energies across layers. It helps analyze how energy is distributed along the depth of the calorimeter, shedding light on the longitudinal aspects of your data.

Phi Profile: The phi profile measures the sum of energies along a single segment point across all layers. This metric allows you to study the angular distribution of energy around the radius.

First Moment Lateral Profile: In the case of the lateral profile, the first moment signifies the average position across radial points. This metric describes the center of mass of energy distribution in the radial direction.

Second Moment Lateral Profile: In the case of the lateral profile, the second moment characterizes the dispersion of energy across radial points.

First Moment Longitudinal Profile: For the longitudinal profile, the first moment represents the average position along the depth (layers) at which the majority of energy is concentrated.

Second Moment Longitudinal Profile: For the longitudinal profile, the second moment represents the spread or dispersion of energy along the depth (layers) of the calorimeter.

Total Energy Per Layer: Examining histograms for the total energy detected in each layer is vital for understanding the energy distribution within the calorimeter, helping to identify any layer-specific patterns.

Cell Energy (Logarithmic): The histogram of cell energies after applying a logarithmic function is important for visualizing the distribution of energy across detector cells, making the data distribution more readable.

Cell Energy (Non-Logarithmic): The non-logarithmic cell energy histogram provides a view of the real, untransformed distribution of cell energies, which can be crucial for understanding the data's inherent characteristics.

Cell Energy (Non-Log) X Log: This metric combines non-logarithmic cell energy with logarithmic scaling, helping to reveal energy distribution in terms of powers of 10, which can provide insights into the energy scale.

Radial Number of Zeros: Understanding occurrences of absolute zero cell energies at a single radius point is vital for identifying and addressing data anomalies or irregularities, potentially highlighting issues or artifacts in the dataset.

In the context of our project, the most crucial metrics for effective modeling are the longitudinal and lateral profiles, total energy, and cell distribution. These metrics provide invaluable insights into the intricate patterns and characteristics of energy deposition within the calorimeter. The longitudinal and lateral profiles offer a comprehensive view of spatial energy distribution, while total energy captures the global energy trends. Additionally, cell distribution, examined in both logarithmic and non-logarithmic forms, enables a detailed understanding of energy granularity. Prioritizing these metrics ensures that our model comprehensively represents the complexities of energy distribution, leading to more accurate and reliable predictions, aligning precisely with the core objectives of our research.

8. Results

The following section delves into the outcomes derived from the experiments as mentioned earlier. This detailed examination of results aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the findings and their implications within the context of the project. For the sake of simplicity, four main profiles are discussed: Total Energy, Lateral Profile, Longitudinal Profile and Cell Energy Distribution

Default Baseline - BCE loss + Incident Energy Scaling

As discussed in the experiment, in this experiment incident energy scale with binary cross entropy was studied and studies are as follows:

The implemented technique demonstrates commendable performance in capturing the lateral, longitudinal, and total energy profiles. These aspects of the data distribution are well-represented, reflecting the effectiveness of the approach. However, a notable challenge arises in accurately modeling the cell energy distribution, which remains an area of concern. The difficulty in characterizing the distribution of energy across individual cells raises important considerations for further refinement and optimization of the technique.

Fig.8 Evaluation data profiles for Baseline Experiment

Evidently, the technique encounters difficulty in accurately capturing the right tail of the cell energy distribution. This specific region of the data exhibits deviations or extreme energies that are challenging to model effectively. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the technique performs admirably in capturing other key profiles, such as the lateral, longitudinal, and total energy profiles, which exhibit promising results and demonstrate the model's competency in handling various aspects of the data distribution. The observed challenge in modeling the right tail emphasizes the need for a more nuanced and tailored approach to address this particular aspect of the data.

Zero-centering with MSE loss and tanh activation

Incorporating zero-centering preprocessing as previously discussed in the preprocessing section is pivotal for certain aspects of data preparation. However, it's important to acknowledge that this transformation can have implications for the choice of loss function in model. Specifically, when data values may fall below zero, the use of Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss, which typically handle values ranging from 0 to 1, may not be suitable. In such cases, to accommodate the range of transformed data, it is necessary to replace the last layer activation from sigmoid to tanh.

By transitioning from sigmoid to tanh activation, the model is better equipped to handle data values that extend beyond the binary classification boundaries of 0 to 1. Additionally, employing Mean Square Error (MSE) loss aligns with this change, as it is well-suited for reconstruction tasks, making it a more appropriate choice when dealing with data that includes negative values.

Fig.9 Evaluation data profiles for Standardization with MSE loss experiment

The results reveal a notable discrepancy with the Mean Square Error (MSE) loss, where the loss function converges, but the model fails to learn effectively. This discrepancy underscores the inadequacy of MSE loss in capturing data deviations and nuances, particularly in the complex cell energy distribution. Additionally, the implementation of zero-centering preprocessing doesn't significantly alter the data's complexity, indicating that this preprocessing alone doesn't enhance the model's capacity to learn the distribution

Total Energy per Layer Scaling

As discussed earlier, the approach of dividing cell energies by the total energy per layer, as employed in the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" preprocessing technique, serves as a simplification strategy for the problem. By decoupling the complexity of accurately predicting total energy per layer, this method significantly enhances the model's capacity to achieve exceptional profiles and accelerates the convergence process. This is primarily because the total energy serves as valuable prior information for the model. However, despite these advantages, it is noteworthy that this approach still grapples with accurately predicting the cell energy distribution, indicating that additional modifications or techniques may be required to address the complexities inherent in this specific aspect of the data.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.10 Evaluation data profiles for Total Energy Scaling Experiment

The results clearly demonstrate a marked difference in the performance of the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" approach compared to other techniques. Notably, it achieves exceptional profiles in approximately half the number of steps, indicating its efficiency in capturing key aspects of the data distribution. These results highlight the overall success of the method in modeling various profiles, which are notably superior to other strategies employed. However, the persistent challenge in accurately predicting the cell energy distribution, despite these positive outcomes, remains a significant concern. This observation underscores the complex nature of modeling cell energy data and the need for further investigation to address this specific challenge effectively.

Maximum Energy per Layer Scaling

As previously discussed, the "Maximum Energy Per Layer Scaling" approach offers a valuable simplification strategy by decoupling the complexity of predicting maximum energy per layer. This approach demonstrates remarkable success in achieving profiles, with rapid convergence due to the provision of total energy as prior information to the model. Notably, it excels not only in capturing profiles but also in addressing the challenging aspect of cell energy distribution. However, it is important to recognize that predicting maximum energies independently poses a level of complexity similar to that of cell energies. Given this level of complexity, further pursuit of

modeling maximum energies as a separate problem is not pursued for further experimentation in the current study.

Fig.11 Evaluation data profiles for Maximum Energy per layer Scaling Experiment

The results clearly indicate that the modeling approach employed successfully captures the distribution of cell energies to a high degree of accuracy. This accomplishment, however, comes with a minor trade-off in the precision of other profiles. While cell energies are represented exceptionally well, there is a slight compromise in the modeling of other key profiles.

Mean Square Error Loss

The observations highlighted in the zero-centering section and illustrated in the accompanying figure 9 reveals a consistent trend across different preprocessing techniques for MSE loss, regardless of the type of preprocessing applied, exhibiting a similar behavior. Rather than effectively learning the distribution, MSE loss tends to gravitate towards attaining the means of the distribution. This consistent pattern underscores a limitation of MSE loss in capturing the nuances and variations within the data. While it may excel in minimizing the discrepancy between predicted and actual mean values, it falls short in fully representing the intricacies of the data distribution, emphasizing the need for alternative loss functions that align more closely with the research objectives.

L1 Loss

As previously discussed in the preprocessing section, the utilization of L1 loss is geared towards capturing sharp deviations within the data. While the results reflect its effectiveness in successfully capturing various profiles, there is a notable trade-off. Specifically, the L1 loss, which prioritizes sharp deviations, tends to result in an overall underestimation of the energy.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.12 Evaluation data profiles for L1 loss Experiment

The results provide a clear perspective on the modeling outcomes, revealing that the overall energies are underestimated.

Maximum Mean Discrepancy Loss

As previously discussed, the adoption of Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) loss was motivated by the aim to minimize the distance between the features of input and generated data distributions. However, the results reveal that this approach does not exhibit the expected improvement in performance. Instead, it falls short in multiple aspects: it underestimates the energy, fails to accurately capture cell energies, and lacks the ability to generalize effectively. The observation that MMD loss, while ensuring features' distance reduction, also generalizes and overlooks high-energy cells is a crucial insight. This generalization inadvertently leads to an overall

underestimation of cell energy, emphasizing the complex and nuanced nature of the data distribution.

The results further shed light on the limitations of the MMD loss approach in effectively modeling the data distribution. Despite its initial promise of reducing feature distance between input and generated data, the inability to capture high-energy cells, along with an overall underestimation of energy, highlights the challenges in striking the right balance between generalization and precision.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.13 Evaluation data profiles for Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) loss Experiment

These findings emphasize the intricacies of modeling complex data and underscore the importance of exploring alternative techniques which penalize more for high cell energies.

Weighted Binary Cross Entropy(WBCE) Loss

The utilization of Weighted Binary Cross-Entropy (WBCE) loss in this project is instrumental in giving more weightage to high cell energies, effectively addressing the specific challenge of capturing these high-energy cells. This weighting strategy results in an overestimation of overall

energies but remarkably enhances the model's ability to capture cell energies. This outcome demonstrates a key insight: the weighted approach to loss functions, which prioritizes certain aspects of the data, can indeed offer significant benefits. By emphasizing high-energy cells, this method contributes to a more accurate representation of the data's complexities, particularly in the context of cell energy distribution. These findings underscore the importance of judiciously weighing loss functions to tailor them to the specific nuances and objectives of the research, ultimately leading to improved model performance.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.14 Evaluation data profiles for Weighted Binary Cross Entropy (WBCE) loss Experiment

The results consistently show an overestimation of overall energies in both the lateral and longitudinal profiles. However, this overestimation is accompanied by a notable success in capturing cell energies. This trade-off is indicative of the modeling approach, where the prioritization of accurately modeling cell energies results in a slight compromise regarding the overall energy estimation.

Weighted Mean Square Error(WMSE) Loss

The utilization of Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss has yielded highly promising results. WMSE loss stands out as the most effective loss function employed, successfully capturing all the key profiles with only a minimal trade-off observed in the total energies graph. This outcome is

particularly noteworthy, as it underscores the critical role of WMSE loss in achieving the project's specific objectives. By effectively balancing the modeling of different data characteristics, WMSE loss emerges as a pivotal tool that aligns closely with the unique challenges and goals of this research, showcasing its potential for enhanced model performance in this context.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.15 Evaluation data profiles for Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss Experiment

Remarkably, the utilization of Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss within this project has resulted in superior outcomes when compared to all previously studied loss functions. It demonstrates a notable capacity to capture all key profiles with greater precision and effectiveness, with slight compromise in total energy result.

Total Energy Scaling + Weighted Loss Function

In the final phase of experimentation, a combination of the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" preprocessing technique and the Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss function was implemented, along with the utilization of the softmax output activation function. This amalgamation of strategies culminated in a remarkable achievement: the successful capture of all key profiles with unparalleled accuracy. Among all the losses and preprocessing strategies examined throughout the project, this particular combination stands out as the most effective. Its ability to comprehensively model different data characteristics and attain the highest level of

accuracy emphasizes its pivotal role in achieving the research objectives and establishing itself as the most successful approach in this unique context.

Lateral Profile

Longitudinal Profile

Cell Energy Distribution

Total Energy

Fig.16 Evaluation data profiles for Total Energy Scaling + WMSE loss Experiment

The results, as depicted in the figures, provide clear and compelling evidence of the effectiveness of the combination of the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" preprocessing technique, Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss function, and the softmax output activation. This amalgamation of strategies excels in capturing all profiles with remarkable precision, showcasing its exceptional ability to outperform all other methods studied in this project. What sets this approach apart is its capacity to significantly capture the data's nuances and complexities given the accuracy of predicting total energies separately.

9. Future Work

In the context of future work, several promising avenues remain unexplored due to time constraints during the current phase of our experiment. One compelling direction for improvement involves a more nuanced implementation of Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) on different layers of the encoder's distribution. This enhancement aims to refine the sensitivity of the model to variations in specific features, potentially leading to more accurate and robust mesh response regeneration.

Another area of exploration is the incorporation of a weighted L1 loss, offering a finer control over the importance assigned to different elements within the reconstruction process. This adaptive weighting mechanism could be particularly beneficial when certain aspects of the mesh response hold greater significance in the context of calorimeter studies.

Additionally, an intriguing prospect for future work involves the integration of a discriminative loss function during training. This approach entails approximating an unknown objective function using a neural network, enabling the model to discern and emphasize critical features within the mesh response generation process. By incorporating discriminative elements, we anticipate an enhancement in the model's ability to capture intricate patterns and nuances in calorimeter responses.

These proposed future directions not only underscore the potential for refining our current methodology but also lay the groundwork for further advancements in the application of autoencoder architectures to calorimeter studies. As time and resources permit, these ideas can be systematically explored to contribute to the ongoing evolution of our experimental framework.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, the task of developing a foundational model for fast simulation in the face of a challenging dataset with sparse values proved to be a formidable yet crucial endeavor, particularly in the context of its role as the base for Large Hadron Collider experiments. Throughout the research, it became evident that the right combination of preprocessing and objective function is key to success. Among the various experiments conducted, the "Total Energy Per Layer Scaling" preprocessing technique and Weighted Mean Square Error (WMSE) loss function stood out as the most effective strategies. When used together, they streamlined the modeling process, captured intricate data profiles with remarkable accuracy, and achieved a balance between different aspects of the data distribution. This tandem approach not only overcame dataset challenges but also yielded the highest accuracy, highlighting the critical importance of thoughtful preprocessing and the choice of an objective function that aligns with the research objectives. Ultimately, this project paves the way for more accurate and reliable fast simulations, underpinning the groundbreaking experiments of the Large Hadron Collider.

11. Références

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